

CLINICAL AND PARACLINICAL FEATURES AND THE NATURE OF THE COURSE OF EPILEPTIC ENCEPHALOPATHY IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Relevance. Currently, some researchers consider interictal epileptic psychoses as a manifestation of epileptic encephalopathy. Epileptic encephalopathy is a condition where pathologically altered brain electrogenesis is the cause of brain dysfunctions. In which the epileptic process as such leads to progressive dysfunctions of the brain.

Purpose of the study: To study the clinical and paraclinical features and the nature of the course of epileptic encephalopathy in preschool children.

Materials and methods of research: this study was based on the data of examination of 30 children with a diagnosis of epileptic encephalopathy at the age of 3 to 7 years. In this work, we used general clinical, neurological and instrumental research methods (EEG).

Research results. According to the data obtained, we found that 8 children (26.6%) with epileptic encephalopathy were diagnosed with Lennox-Gastaut syndrome, Landau-Kleffner syndrome - in 3 (10%) and in 2 (6.7%) West syndrome. All these children were classified as type I epileptic encephalopathy. The age subdivision revealed that this group included children aged 3 to 7 years, the average age of children was 4.2 ± 0.32 years. Tonic seizures were observed in 11 children (36.67%), among them short-term seizures were recorded in 8 children, which lasted for several seconds. Atypical absence seizures were observed in 5 patients (16.7%), had a relatively gradual onset and end, in contrast to the sudden nature of typical

absences. Atonic seizures were observed in 7 children (23.3%) and were characterized by a sudden and significant loss of postural tone with the involvement of the whole body or only the head muscles. Myoclonic seizures were recorded in 4 patients (13.3%) (nodding, pecking, flinching). Polymorphism of epileptic seizures was observed among 23.3% (7 children) of patients. When analyzing the neurological status, it was found that children with type 1 epileptic encephalopathy are characterized by micro-focal neurological symptoms in the form of: disorders of the cranial nerves, pyramidal insufficiency (tendon hyperreflexia on the one hand, anisotonia, the presence of pathological reflexes), transient coordination disorders (dysmetria when performing coordination samples). With EEG monitoring, 57.2% had a pattern-diffuse slow peak-wave activity bilateral and synchronous with a frequency of 12.5 Hz, with an emphasis on the frontal and temporal lobes. During the wakefulness phase in the interictal period, diffuse slow sharp waves were recorded in 62.4% of children. When studying cognitive function according to Raven's progressive matrices, a high percentage of low intelligence was revealed in comparison with a group of apparently healthy children.

Conclusion: Thus, type I epileptic encephalopathy is characterized by micro-focal neurological disorders with progressive disorders of the cognitive sphere, intelligence, speech and other cerebral functions.